

An Evaluation of Strategies Adopted by Heritage Hotels Rajasthan in Terms of Competition: With Reference to Pink City Jaipur

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Abstract

Competition in the service sector can be explained in terms of the efforts made by any two or more service organizations, acting independently, in order to safeguard and growth their business in positive direction. Here the preserving and allocation of resources is very important as the value of resources in service sector is high, hence the resources are deployed to most high valued use and with great efficiency. This present study focuses on the strategical framework of heritage hotels of Jaipur in order to face the increasing competition. Study is based on primary data; researcher has selected 150 respondents and applied Chi Square test to analyze the data. Findings of this study will certainly benefit the present researcher also present a base for future researchers.

Keywords: Heritage Hotels, Strategies, Competition, Jaipur, Pink City

Introduction

Strategy can be viewed as a scope of a given organization, in the present times and in future as well, to achieve competitive edge and advantage over the competitors. It can also increase the competencies of the organizations over a period of time and also fulfill the expectations of the related stakeholders. **Scholes et al (2005)**. As per **Scholes (2007)**, the above given meaning of strategy can be considered for long term and is future oriented, it also related to the long-term goals of the organization. A strategy is capable of identifying markets for the growth of markets and basis of competition in such markets. **Mintzberg (1987)** gave the different types of strategies as follows:

- Strategy as plan i.e., a direction, guide, course of action - intention rather than actual;
- Strategy as ploy i.e., a maneuver intended to outwit a competitor;

- Strategy as pattern i.e., a consistent pattern of past behavior - realized rather than intended;
- Strategy as position (locating of brands, products, or companies within the conceptual framework of consumers or other stakeholders
- Strategy determined primarily by factors outside the firm; and,
- Strategy as perspective i.e., strategy determined primarily by a master strategist.

Strategy does not only influence the top management of the organization, rather it is very closely related to the functions of each and every individual working in the organization. For example, corporate strategy is related to the overall purpose and scope of the business; business unit strategy is related to how a business competes successfully in a particular market and, operational strategy is related to how each part of the business is organized to deliver the corporate and business-unit level strategic direction and focuses on issues of resources, processes, people. **Arauz (2012)**. Here the corporate strategy is very important to cover the business investors and authentic decision making at top level of the management. Then the business unit strategy is related to the market need like, choice of products, meeting needs of customers, gaining advantage over competitors, exploiting or creating new opportunities among other things. May some amount of uncertainty be present in case of business unit strategy but options are always open for the decision makers. Hence it can be stated that derivation of proper strategy is very important for any given organizations and hotel industry is one of them, in this case a wrong decision can ruin the business in long terms, as this is directly related to the service sector.

Source: <https://www.slideteam.net/types-of-business-strategies-with-activities.html>

Figure 1: Different types of Business Strategies

Competition in Service Industry

Competition in the service sector can be explained in terms of the efforts made by any two or more service organizations, acting independently, in order to safeguard and growth their business in positive direction. Here the preserving and allocation of resources is very important as the value of resources in service sector is high, hence the resources are deployed to most high valued use and with great efficiency. **Stigler (2008)**. On the other hand, competition motivates the firms of service sector to develop new products, services and technologies, which would provide opportunity to consumers for selecting better products and services. In case of service sector, competition is not only in the market, rather it is present within the organization as well, where the employees may compete each other to cater the customer at the first hand and in a better way. Such competition in the service sector increases the facilities for the customer and motivates the competing firms to deal with the deficits of the market. **Armstrong et al (2018)**. If the competition increases in the service sector then its attractiveness is influenced to a particular level and even the profitability is also affected, but the healthy competition will certainly help in defending the firms against the negative forces of the market. **Thompson et al (2002)**. Sustainable competitive advantage is born out of core competencies that yield long term benefit to the company. **Prahalad et al (2010)** define a core competence as an area of specialized expertise that is the result of harmonizing complex streams of technology and work activity.

	Occupational	Personal
Conceptual	Cognitive Competencies <i>Knowledge</i>	Meta Competencies <i>Motives and Traits</i>
Operational	Functional Competencies <i>Skills</i>	Social Competencies <i>Attitudes and Behaviours</i>

Source: Delamare et al 2005

Figure 2: Core Competences of Hotel Industry

Heritage Hotels in Jaipur

At the national, Heritage hotels are divided in the following categories.:

Grand Heritage: This category will cover hotels in residences/havelis/hunting lodges/castles/forts/palaces built prior to 1935. The hotel should have a minimum of 15 rooms (30 beds).

Classic Heritage: This category will cover hotels in residences/havelis/hunting lodges/castles/forts/palaces built after 1935. These hotels should also have a minimum of 15 rooms (30 beds).

Heritage Hotels– This category will cover hotels in residences/havelis/hunting lodges/castles/forts/palaces built after 1950. They should have a minimum of 5 rooms (10 beds).

As far as Jaipur is concerned “Heritage” is the USP (unique selling proposition) of tourism and it plays an important role in the growth of tourism industry in the state of Rajasthan. Heritage of the city influences the economic activities, policies of Government, environment and even society.

Below given heritage hotels of Jaipur city are considered for the purpose of assessment in this present study, these are; Raj Palace, Jai Mahal, Rambagh Palace, Samode Haveli and Narain Niwas Palace.

	<p>Raj Palace Built: 1727 Location: Jaipur, Rajasthan Style: Mughal and Rajput Dynasty: Choumoo Operated by: Gkv Hotel Pvt. Ltd. Heritage Hotel type: Heritage Grand</p>
	<p>Jai Mahal Built: 1745 Location: Jaipur, Rajasthan Style: Rajput and Indo Saracenic Dynasty: Kachhuuaha Rajputs Operated by: Taj group Pvt. Ltd. Heritage Hotel type: Heritage Grand</p>
	<p>Rambagh Palace Built: 1835 Location: Jaipur, Rajasthan Style: Rajput Dynasty: Kacchwaha Operated by : Taj group Pvt. Ltd. Heritage Hotel type : Heritage Grand</p>

	<p>Samode Haveli Built: 1900 Location: Jaipur, Rajasthan Style: Rajput Dynasty: Nathawat Rawals Operated by: Family run hotel Heritage Hotel type: Heritage Classic</p>
	<p>Narain Niwas Palace Built: 1928 Location: Jaipur, Rajasthan Style: Anglo-Indian Operated by : Family run hotel Heritage Hotel type : Heritage Classic</p>

As per the directives and policies of Indian government, many of the old havelis, Palaces, residences, forts and even castles were converted into hotels, in such a scenario preservation of the heritage has remained the top priority, hence all the rooms and place are not opened for the guests in any condition. Here it is important to mention that both the state and central government policies are implacable to business of heritage hotels in the state of Rajasthan and the same are being followed in Jaipur as well. **Levick et al (2007)**. Considering the model of Rajasthan, Indian government has promoted heritage hotels in other states of the country like, Bihar, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Puducherry, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, etc.

Starting from the beginning, heritage hotel industry has remained one of the profit-making business units for the promoters of the same, on the other hand many of the individual owners had identified the opportunity and converted their establishments into heritage hotels, this has remained a lucrative venture for such owners. At this juncture there are two benefits for such individual owners, firstly they started to get revenue from an offbeat building and secondly the old structures used to get maintained. Apart from all other benefits heritage hotels are one of the sources to generate foreign exchange as well. Many of the foreign tourist prefer to visit in these heritage hotels to get the feel of ancient culture and environment. In popular terms, staying in heritage hotels is considered as a luxury experience and there are authentic reasons for the same, like, the history behind the structure and ambience, the feeling of being equated to the old kings and queens, proud and privilege of staying in these cultural places, then the service standards are very high in such places.

Efforts of the Tourism Ministry of Rajasthan

Tourist from abroad is fascinated with life style of the Indian rajas and maharajas of the past. The heritage hotels provide them an opportunity to experience for themselves that life style in the same settings. However, because of the high costs only high budget tourists can afford them. A prime objective of the tourism policy during the Eighth Plan is to attract high spenders from

countries US, Europe and Japan. The scheme of heritage hotels fits in well to achieve the objective.

In order to promote the scheme, the department of tourism has provided the following incentives:

- Tax Exemptions
- Depreciation
- Interest Subsidy
- Foreign Exchange Incentive Quota
- Concessional Customs Duty

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this present study is to evaluate the effect of marketing strategies to promote heritage hotels on tourist and growth of the business in turn.

Hypothesis

H₀: There is a positive and significant impact of marketing strategies to promote heritage hotels on foreign tourists.

H₁: There is a no significant impact of marketing strategies to promote heritage hotels on foreign tourists.

Research Methodology

On the basis of objectives framed and hypothesis prepared, the researcher had considered both the exploratory and descriptive research designs i.e., most part of this study is based on primary data collected from the foreign tourists visiting Jaipur as a tourist destination and staying in heritage hotels. Then on the other hand secondary data is being used to a substantial level. Most of the data was collected from the nearby places of heritage hotels i.e., both the urban and rural places are observed in the process. As this study is based on the evaluation of strategies adopted to promote the heritage hotels and effect of the same on foreign tourists, hence the researcher considered primary and secondary data both.

Sampling

Total 150 foreign tourist were considered as respondents on the basis of arrivals of tourists on Jaipur international airport, some of the essential conditions were considered as restriction, like:

- Visitors are coming to explore Rajasthan only
- Married
- Not connected to any tour operator
- Visitors should be individual and not in group

Tools used

In order to collect firsthand information from the respondents, the researcher has used a detailed questionnaire, the various question of the same include questions of different nature like multiple choice, direct, dichotomous nature. This questionnaire was exercised with the respondents with their consent looking at the availability of their time.

Then for the analysis of data the researcher has applied Chi Square test on the collected data, this test was used as the researcher wants to find the variation in responses of the sample units. All the responses were categorized and tested accordingly.

The researcher has used SPSS Ver. 22.0 to perform the tests.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

On the above given lines of study, the researcher has collected the data and respective tests were performed on the same. Detailed analysis and interpretation of collected is given below.

Summary of Chi Square (χ^2)

Test Summary								
Awareness								
Test Component (Income)					Test Component (Age)			
	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Courteous	Culinary Heritage is present	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Courteous	Culinary Heritage is present
Calculated Value	1.227	.892	.679	3.418	.883	.583	2.907	1.240
Table Value	2.537	1.581	2.631	4.818	1.761	1.367	2.017	2.792
Frequency of Visit								
Test Component (Purpose of Visit)					Test Component (Age)			
	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Courteous	Culinary Heritage is present	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Courteous	Culinary Heritage is present
Calculated Value	1.589	1.027	3.507	1.227	1.522	2.618	3.903	1.784
Table Value	3.557	1.572	4.618	2.393	2.715	.948	2.604	1.818
Purpose of Visit								
Test Component (Purpose of Visit)					Test Component (Age)			
	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Courteous	Culinary Heritage is present	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Courteous	Culinary Heritage is present

							eous	present
Calculate d Value	1.539	2.670	1.483	3.637	2.558	1.070	2.829	1.632
Table Value	1.907	3.509	2.083	2.918	3.463	1.918	3.889	1.532
Overall Experience								
	Test Component (Purpose of Visit)				Test Component (Age)			
	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Courteo us	Culinary Heritage is present	Ambience is good	Feeling of Royal Heritage	Staff is Court eous	Culinary Heritage is present
Calculate d Value	2.928	1.146	2.575	.928	2.685	3.975	3.976	2.658
Table Value	3.545	7.151	4.447	5.745	5.978	2.013	5.432	4.618

Interpretation

In the above given Chi Square test results, it can be found that in most of the cases calculated value is less than the table value, this shows that most of the respondents were agreed to the point in question and they certainly enjoyed their visit to the heritage hotels of Jaipur.

In the above test result decision rule is ‘If the table value is more than the calculated value then the hypothesis is accepted and vice-versa’.

In the light of above decision rule some of the components are required to be elaborated, like in case of awareness, most of the respondents were agreed to the point in question, based on their age and income group. In some of the cases like ambience and royal feeling the test results are almost similar, this is a positive sign but also shows that perception is below the expectations.

Then on the other hand, in case of ‘Frequency of visit’ courtesy of staff and royal feeling shows negative results, although the test values are not negative enough to reject the hypothesis. It can be stated that most of respondents were almost satisfied from their stay in the selected heritage hotel, even some of the respondents claimed that food was very spicy as compared to their appetite.

Then in case of purpose of visit and overall experience, the respondents were very much satisfied with the facilities and amenities present in the heritage hotels and they are willing to visit again to the same heritage hotel.

Conclusion

In this present study the researcher had tried to find the relevance of marketing strategies of heritage hotels and traffic of foreign tourist, on the basis of the same. On the other hand, it also includes the components of marketing, tourism, and hospitality academics and practitioners,

heritage experiential quality, heritage value, heritage image, and visitor satisfaction. It was found in the process of study that apart from the heritage value, ambience, etc. it is also required that the heritage hotels should promote behavioral intention on different types of media along with their respective culinary practices. This is certainly going to increase the value of heritage tourism of Jaipur all around the globe. Findings of the study also state that heritage hotel practitioners should ensure that their site provides an exceptional heritage experience that will enhance its image. The visitors will thus perceive high heritage value and have a higher level of satisfaction. Furthermore, those constructs will improve the visitor intention to re-visit and re-patronize the service.

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